

a) On the (")Random(") - b) The Manner in Which Determinism and Free Will Might Not Be Incompatible:

a) The 'random' might be nothing more than a product of our ignorance ("It happened to rain" -> it did not "happen by chance" at all; I simply lacked access to the requisite knowledge - information to predict it).

b) Determinism could perhaps also coexist with free will in the following manner: If the causal chain that makes me choose whatever I choose is so entangled and, in reality (by extension), unified with all the events of the universe (excluding God, Who is not an event, but Being), then predicting what I will do (and thus the abolition of my free will) would require an observer outside the (rest of the) Universal Becoming, which means it can only be (at most) God.

Essentially, what I am stating relates to the "Game of the World" (for instance, two people playing chess, no matter how great their self-awareness, as long as they lack access to the whole —meaning, in this case, Also the opponent— they cannot, under any circumstances, truly KNOW what the chessboard will look like when the game ends).